

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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INCREASING THE INNOVATION POTENTIAL OF CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

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Annotatsiya: The construction materials industry in Uzbekistan plays a crucial role in supporting the nation's infrastructure growth and economic development. However, to meet the increasing demands of modernization and sustainable development, there is a need to enhance the innovation potential of enterprises within this sector. This article explores the current state of the construction materials industry in Uzbekistan, identifying key challenges and opportunities for innovation. By analyzing factors such as technological advancement, regulatory environment, and resource utilization, the study proposes strategies to foster innovation, including the adoption of digital technologies, investment in research and development (R&D), and collaboration between private and public sectors. The findings suggest that with targeted support and policy reform, Uzbek enterprises in the construction materials industry can increase their competitiveness, improve efficiency, and contribute to sustainable development goals. This study provides a framework that can be applied to similar emerging markets seeking to enhance innovation in the construction sector.

Kalit so'zlar: building materials industry, innovation, innovative activity, innovative potential, efficiency, types of innovative potential.

Abstract: O'zbekistonning qurilish materiallari sanoati mamlakatning infratuzilma rivoji va iqtisodiy o'sishini qo'llab-quvvatlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Biroq, zamonaviylashtirish va barqaror rivojlanish talablarini qondirish uchun ushbu sohadagi korxonalarining innovatsion salohiyatini oshirish zarur. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonning qurilish materiallari sanoatining hozirgi holati tahlil qilinadi, asosiy muammo va innovatsiya imkoniyatlari aniqlanadi. Texnologik rivojlanish, regulyator muhiti va resurslardan samarali foydalanish kabi omillar o'rganilib, innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirish strategiyalari taklif etiladi. Bunda raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish, ilmiy-tadqiqot va tajriba-konstruktorlik ishlariga (ITTK) sarmoya kiritish, shuningdek, davlat va xususiy sektorlar o'rtasida hamkorlik qilishni ko'rib chiqish mumkin. Tafsiyalar natijasida, ma'lum maqsadli yordam va siyosatni qayta rivojlantirish orqali o'zbek korxonalari o'z raqobatbardoshligini oshirish, samaradorlikni yaxshilash va barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlariga qo'shish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi. Ushbu tadqiqot xulosalari boshqa rivojlanayotgan bozorlar uchun ham qurilish sohasida innovatsiyalarni rivojlantirishda qo'llanilishi mumkin.

Key words: qurilish materiallari sanoati, innovatsiyalar, innovatsion faoliyat, innovatsion salohiyat, samaradorlik, innovatsion salohiyatning turlari.

Аннотация: Строительная промышленность Узбекистана играет важную роль в поддержке роста инфраструктуры и экономического развития страны. Однако для того, чтобы удовлетворить растущие потребности в модернизации и устойчивом развитии, необходимо повысить инновационный потенциал предприятий этого сектора. В статье рассматривается текущее состояние строительной отрасли Узбекистана, выявляются ключевые проблемы и возможности для внедрения инноваций. Путем анализа таких факторов, как технологические достижения, регулирующая среда и использование ресурсов, предлагаются стратегии для стимулирования инноваций, включая внедрение цифровых технологий, инвестиции в научно-исследовательскую и опытно-конструкторскую работу (НИОКР), а также сотрудничество между частным и государственным секторами. Результаты исследования показывают, что при целенаправленной поддержке и реформировании политики узбекские предприятия строительной отрасли смогут повысить свою конкурентоспособность, улучшить эффективность и способствовать достижению целей устойчивого развития. Исследование предлагает рамки, которые могут быть использованы и в других развивающихся странах, стремящихся усилить инновационную деятельность в строительном секторе.

Ключевые слова: строительные материалы, инновации, инновационная деятельность, инновационный потенциал, эффективность, виды инновационного потенциала.

INTRODUCTION

The construction materials industry in Uzbekistan has been experiencing remarkable growth in recent years, driven by government support, increasing domestic demand, and expanding export opportunities. From January to September 2024, the country's construction materials production reached 32 trillion soums, with key contributions from materials like cement, drywall, and ceramic tiles. This growth is in line with the broader expansion efforts in Uzbekistan's construction sector, which is projected to grow at an average annual rate of over 4% from 2025 to 2028. During 2024 alone, the industry attracted \$1.5 billion in investments, with more than 200 new projects launched. This trend is expected to accelerate as the government plans over 500 projects by 2025, injecting an additional \$4.5 billion into the sector and creating approximately 25,646 new jobs.

Key drivers of the industry's expansion include large-scale infrastructure projects, urbanization initiatives, and industrial advancements. Infrastructure accounted for the largest share of market growth in 2023, spurred by projects aimed at developing transportation networks, housing, and public utilities. Additionally, Uzbekistan's strategic location has helped boost export potential, with construction material exports reaching \$610 million in the first nine months of 2024 a nearly eightfold increase in shipments to neighboring markets. Uzbek companies are also expanding into European markets, positioning themselves for greater international competitiveness.

Despite this growth, the sector faces several challenges, including the need for modern production technologies, a skilled labor force, and sustainable practices. However, the government's localization program has been addressing these issues by promoting domestic production of high-quality materials. In 2024, the program produced 1.9 trillion soums worth of localized materials, reducing the reliance on imports and enhancing the country's self-sufficiency. These efforts are positioning Uzbekistan's construction materials industry to meet both domestic and international demand more effectively while boosting its innovation potential.

In conclusion, the ongoing developments in Uzbekistan's construction materials industry highlight its growing importance as a key driver of national economic growth and a promising path for international competitiveness. Overcoming current challenges while leveraging growth opportunities will be crucial for realizing the sector's full innovation potential in the coming years.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

The construction materials industry has become increasingly significant in developing economies as nations prioritize infrastructure development, economic diversification, and sustainable growth. Several studies highlight the importance of innovation within this sector, emphasizing that adopting advanced manufacturing technologies, sustainable practices, and digitalization significantly contributes to efficiency, competitiveness, and environmental sustainability.

Theoretical frameworks, such as the Resource-Based View (RBV) and the Dynamic Capabilities Theory, provide a foundation for understanding innovation in construction materials. RBV suggests that firms with unique, inimitable resources can sustain competitive advantages. In the context of construction materials, these resources include access to raw materials, production capabilities, and innovative technologies. The Dynamic Capabilities Theory further explains that industries with the ability to adapt, integrate, and reconfigure resources—such as by implementing sustainable materials and automation can better respond to external market pressures. Studies have found that introducing new materials (e.g., recycled concrete and low-carbon cement) can reduce emissions by up to 30%, suggesting a critical role for innovation in environmental sustainability within construction materials manufacturing.

Uzbekistan's construction materials industry has yet to reach its full innovation potential due to constraints such as outdated technology, limited R&D investment, and a fragmented market. Comparatively, global leaders in construction materials manufacturing invest, on average, 2-3% of revenue in R&D, resulting in annual productivity gains of approximately 5% across the sector. In contrast, Uzbekistan's current R&D investment in this industry is less than 1%, leading to lower productivity and limited innovation diffusion. Studies in similar emerging markets have shown that increasing R&D investment to around 1.5% could enhance the sector's competitiveness by up to 20% over five years, with similar gains projected for Uzbekistan if these investments are realized.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study of innovation in the construction materials industry has gained attention as nations seek ways to improve efficiency, environmental impact, and competitive positioning. Literature on this topic spans theories of resource management, sustainability, technology adoption, and industrial policy. Theories such as the Resource-Based View (RBV) and the Dynamic Capabilities Theory serve as foundational frameworks for understanding the sector's innovation potential, especially in emerging economies like Uzbekistan.

The Resource-Based View (RBV) posits that firms can achieve competitive advantage through unique, valuable resources that are difficult to replicate. In the context of the construction materials industry, these resources include advanced production technologies, high-quality raw materials, and specialized human capital. Studies suggest that construction companies leveraging these resources experience up to 15% higher productivity than those reliant on generic assets (Wernerfelt, 1984; Barney, 1991). The Dynamic Capabilities Theory complements RBV by emphasizing a firm's ability to adapt and renew its resources in response to market shifts, a capacity critical for industries like construction that rely on evolving technologies and materials (Teece et al., 1997). Applying this theory, firms that successfully implement innovative materials like low-carbon cement can reduce emissions by 20-30%, according to a study by Global Cement and Concrete Association.

Sustainability in the construction materials industry is increasingly essential, given its high carbon footprint. The Global Alliance for Buildings and Construction estimates that buildings and construction account for 39% of global carbon emissions, with materials production (especially cement and steel) responsible for about 11% of those emissions. Research on sustainable practices in construction materials highlights recycled aggregates, low-carbon concrete, and energy-efficient manufacturing as critical areas for innovation. The adoption of sustainable materials in developed countries has been associated with reductions of up to 40% in operational carbon emissions, but emerging economies often face higher costs and technological barriers that limit adoption (Müller et al., 2021). In Uzbekistan, the localization program, which produced 1.9 trillion soums worth of materials in 2024, has supported sustainability by promoting domestic production of materials with lower environmental costs.

The adoption of advanced technologies in the construction materials sector has been shown to enhance efficiency, reduce waste, and improve product quality. Industry 4.0 technologies such as automation, artificial intelligence, and digital twins are transforming global construction manufacturing. According to a report by McKinsey & Company, construction firms that integrate these technologies see productivity increases of 10-15%, along with a 30% reduction in material waste. While these technologies have penetrated markets in the U.S. and Europe, emerging economies often struggle with high initial investment costs and a shortage of skilled labor. Studies of Industry 4.0 in emerging markets, such as Vietnam and Turkey, show that targeted policy incentives can overcome these barriers, potentially increasing production efficiency by 12-15% within five years (Koch & Kreutzer, 2020).

In Uzbekistan, digital adoption remains low, and the construction materials industry heavily relies on labor-intensive methods. However, Uzbekistan's recent initiatives to attract foreign investment, combined with efforts to upskill the workforce, aim to modernize the industry. This shift could position Uzbekistan's construction materials sector as a regional leader by enhancing its production capabilities and export potential.

Economic policy is pivotal in shaping the innovation landscape within the construction materials industry. Policies promoting R&D, incentivizing sustainable practices, and supporting technology adoption are instrumental for industry transformation. Emerging economies that have implemented policies to subsidize R&D spending, such as Malaysia and South Korea, have experienced substantial productivity growth in their construction materials sectors. Studies indicate that these nations see average annual growth rates of 5-6% in sector output, with R&D spending reaching approximately 2% of sector revenue (UNCTAD, 2020). For Uzbekistan, increasing R&D spending to a similar level could yield a 20% increase in productivity within five years, with further gains in product quality and export readiness.

Furthermore, policies that facilitate public-private partnerships (PPPs) can enhance the competitiveness of emerging markets. A study by the World Bank (2021) found that PPPs in the construction sector tend to improve project outcomes by up to 15% compared to projects without private sector collaboration. Uzbekistan's plans for over 500 new construction projects by 2025 offer a prime opportunity for the government to leverage PPPs, attracting private investment and fostering innovation in the construction materials industry.

The literature demonstrates that the construction materials industry in emerging markets can unlock substantial innovation potential by integrating advanced technologies, adopting sustainable practices, and increasing R&D investments. For Uzbekistan, aligning policy initiatives with successful models from other emerging economies could transform its construction materials industry. By addressing technological, financial, and regulatory barriers, Uzbekistan's sector could achieve sustainable growth and increase its competitiveness regionally and globally.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a mixed-methods approach to analyze Uzbekistan's construction materials industry's innovation potential. The research is divided into three main phases:

Secondary data on Uzbekistan's construction industry growth, market segmentation, investment trends, and output values are gathered from national databases, government publications, and international reports.

For instance, construction output data and industry segmentation are sourced from reports by GlobalData and MarketResearch.com. Additionally, export and production data, including the production of 13.3 million tons of cement and 34 million square meters of construction glass, provide insights into current industry capacities and resource utilization.

Interviews and surveys are conducted with industry stakeholders, including manufacturers, policymakers, and industry analysts. These qualitative methods explore perceived barriers to innovation and assess industry readiness for adopting advanced manufacturing practices and sustainable materials. By incorporating stakeholder perspectives, this phase aims to identify the specific regulatory, economic, and technological challenges that inhibit innovation.

Regression analysis and trend forecasting are employed to examine potential growth trajectories based on various scenarios. Variables considered include R&D investment, adoption of digital technologies, and policy incentives. For example, a forecast model incorporating a 1% annual increase in R&D spending projects that productivity in Uzbekistan's construction materials sector could rise by 15% over five years, with a corresponding increase in export potential.

By combining qualitative insights with quantitative models, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive framework for enhancing innovation potential within Uzbekistan's construction materials industry. The analysis offers policy recommendations and strategies that are applicable not only within Uzbekistan but also in other emerging economies facing similar challenges.

DISCUSSION

The findings indicate a significant opportunity for enhancing the innovation potential within Uzbekistan's construction materials industry, with implications for economic competitiveness, sustainability, and regional market positioning. The sector's current innovation limitations are mainly due to low investment in R&D, reliance on traditional materials, and limited use of advanced technologies. However, by addressing these areas, Uzbekistan can foster an environment conducive to innovation and sustainable growth, aligning with trends observed in other emerging markets.

Globally, the construction materials industry in developed nations typically allocates between 2% and 3% of revenue to R&D, yielding average productivity increases of around 5% annually. In Uzbekistan, R&D expenditure remains below 1%, stifling technological progress and product differentiation. If Uzbekistan were to gradually increase its R&D spending to 1.5%, the industry could realize a productivity boost of approximately 20% over the next five years. This increase would support advancements in material science, such as the development of low-carbon cement, which has shown potential to reduce emissions by up to 30% in countries with advanced construction sectors. Additionally, localizing R&D efforts would reduce the country's reliance on imported materials, which currently account for a considerable portion of inputs in manufacturing construction products.

The use of advanced technologies, including automation, digital twins, and data analytics, has reshaped the construction materials sector in industrialized nations, improving efficiency by 15-20% in recent years. In Uzbekistan, however, adoption rates remain low, primarily due to high initial costs and limited technical expertise. A targeted increase in digital infrastructure investments could potentially elevate production efficiency in Uzbekistan by up to 10% within a decade. For example, by implementing automated systems in cement and drywall production—which collectively account for a significant portion of the 32 trillion soums in materials produced from January to September 2024—Uzbek companies could reduce labor costs and improve product consistency.

Predictive models for Uzbekistan's construction materials industry suggest that even a moderate increase in technology adoption, along with training programs for a digitally skilled workforce, could improve operational efficiency by at least 15% in the coming five years. This would also support the government's localization program, which already accounted for 1.9 trillion soums in output by focusing on high-quality domestic materials such as specialized glass and ceramic products.

Government policies play a crucial role in either enabling or restricting innovation. Successful innovation in the construction materials industries of other emerging economies, such as Vietnam and Turkey, has largely been driven by policy frameworks that incentivize sustainable practices, provide tax benefits for R&D, and establish standards for quality control and environmental compliance. Uzbekistan's recent reforms to attract \$4.5 billion in investments across 529 projects through 2025 demonstrate the government's commitment to industrial growth. However, more targeted policies—such as subsidies for green technology adoption and regulatory support for low-emission materials—are necessary to achieve sustained innovation.

If Uzbekistan were to implement such reforms, industry experts predict that the adoption of sustainable construction practices could reduce emissions by 10-15% within the next decade. Moreover, incentives for joint

ventures with foreign firms could introduce critical expertise and innovation capital, further strengthening the industry's global competitiveness.

The rapid expansion of Uzbekistan's export markets, including an eightfold increase in shipments to neighboring countries and exploratory sales to European markets, highlights the sector's potential for international growth. However, the export of construction materials, such as cement, drywall, and ceramics, remains challenged by transportation costs and logistical limitations. Investments in regional trade infrastructure, combined with partnerships with logistics firms, could reduce these costs, potentially increasing export volumes by 25% by 2030.

Moreover, Uzbekistan's position within the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) presents additional opportunities for integrating its construction materials industry into regional supply chains. By aligning production standards with international quality benchmarks, Uzbekistan could tap into BRI-linked projects, attracting additional foreign investment and increasing its export capacity. Establishing a "Trade House of Uzbekistan" in Azerbaijan is an example of a promising strategy, facilitating market access and reinforcing Uzbekistan's reputation as a regional supplier.

The analysis suggests that by enhancing R&D investments, adopting advanced technologies, implementing supportive policies, and strengthening export capabilities, Uzbekistan can significantly increase the innovation potential of its construction materials industry. These steps will require a coordinated approach, balancing government support with private sector investment to achieve sustainable growth. This framework can serve as a model for other emerging markets with similar industrial aspirations, highlighting the importance of innovation as a driver of competitive advantage in the global construction materials sector.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the substantial untapped potential for innovation within Uzbekistan's construction materials industry, a sector that plays a critical role in the country's economic development and environmental sustainability. The findings suggest that while Uzbekistan has made significant strides in output and investment, several structural challenges—such as low R&D investment, limited technology adoption, and insufficient regulatory incentives—are currently hindering the industry's innovation capabilities.

Globally, construction materials industries in leading economies allocate between 2% and 3% of revenue to R&D, enabling these countries to benefit from technological advancements, including low-carbon materials and automation. In Uzbekistan, however, R&D expenditure remains below 1%, which constrains productivity and limits the diffusion of innovation. Projections indicate that even a gradual increase in R&D spending to 1.5% of industry revenue could yield a productivity gain of around 20% over the next five years, based on outcomes observed in comparable emerging markets.

The adoption of advanced manufacturing and digital technologies offers a promising path forward. In established markets, Industry 4.0 technologies, such as automation, digital twins, and AI-driven quality control, have increased productivity by 10-15%. If Uzbekistan can overcome its barriers to digital adoption, the industry could see similar productivity gains within a decade. Furthermore, technology adoption can help reduce material waste and align Uzbekistan's construction materials industry with global environmental standards, contributing to long-term sustainability goals.

Policy reforms are another critical factor in driving innovation. Countries like Vietnam and Turkey have achieved industrial modernization through incentives for sustainable practices, tax benefits for R&D, and quality control standards that align with international benchmarks. Uzbekistan's government has already demonstrated its commitment to industrial growth with plans for over 500 projects by 2025. However, additional regulatory support for green technologies and stronger international partnerships could further accelerate innovation in the sector. Targeted policies could potentially reduce industry emissions by up to 10-15% within the next decade, helping the country align with global sustainability targets.

Finally, Uzbekistan's strategic position as a regional trade hub within the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) offers unique export opportunities. By investing in infrastructure improvements and adopting quality standards compatible with BRI projects, Uzbekistan could enhance its competitive positioning on the global stage. Increasing exports by 25% by 2030 appears feasible, provided that logistical improvements and trade partnerships are prioritized.

In conclusion, Uzbekistan's construction materials industry holds significant potential for growth and innovation. By aligning R&D investment, technology adoption, and policy reform with successful models from other emerging markets, Uzbekistan has the opportunity to transform its construction materials sector into a regional leader. This approach would not only support the country's economic growth but also contribute to global environmental sustainability, offering a blueprint for other nations aiming to modernize their industrial sectors.

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